

Hearing Voices in the Archive: Wartime Correspondence and the Road to Expanded Source Criticism

Milan van Lange (with input from Carlijn Keijzer)

NIOD Institute for War, Holocaust, and Genocide Studies,
Amsterdam, The Netherlands.

This contribution reflects on digital transformations and the ‘analog’ provenance of historical archival collections of so-called ‘egodocuments’.¹ The increasing availability and usage of digital-born or digitised records in historical scholarship has created a momentum to critically reflect on transformative interactions with(in) the archive when doing (digital) historical research. The recently digitised wartime letters collection (1935-1950), held by the NIOD Institute for War, Holocaust, and Genocide Studies, serves as a case study to illustrate a need to expand current practices of source criticism in historical scholarship in the digital age. During the workshop, I will present some exemplary cases and offer some guiding principles and strategies for what I call ‘expanded source criticism’.²

To date, many historians inadequately recognize the influence of record-keeping and digitisation actors as co-creators of the archival collections from which they derive their ‘sources’. When they examine, for example, situatedness, this is mostly done from the perspective of the initial historical actor or research subject. This habit implies that historians perceive professional record-keepers or archivists as no more than neutral guardians of old paper. This perception seems to suit the dominant professional self-

image of historians, as it makes them the main actors uncovering the yet unexplored archive and doing the truly new and groundbreaking interpretative work. This internalized misconception leads to overlooking the important implications of curatorial actions for the records which historians use as sources. This observation, especially given the recent increase in archival digitisation projects, calls for more self-reflection among historians and a deeper interest in and investigation of the work of record-keeping agents, such as the archivists curating and digitizing their source materials.³

In this paper, I combine multiple empirical case studies, based on war letter (sub)collections, with theories and methodological approaches from the field of archival studies.⁴ This can be considered a first step in developing an analytical framework to gain a better understanding of the impact of diverse and interconnected curatorial practices, digitisation, and other and (re-)contextualizing processes through time.⁵ Enhancing historical scholars’ abilities to integrate archival theory in source criticism when working with digital-born or digitised sources is helpful in comprehending complex historical records collections of (digitised) ‘egodocuments’ and their value, meaning, and characteristics as source material in (digital) historical research.

An important premise of this article is therefore that the wartime letters under scrutiny are more than a reflection of the experiences, perceptions, and emotions of their initial authors. They are also shaped by prevailing time- and place-bound cultural and social conventions of their creators, custodians, and curators. This context is analyzed by unraveling how different and mutually interacting transformations added new layers to the shape, context, and meaning of ‘egodocuments’

¹ The term ‘egodocuments’ refers to varied, non-elite, often autobiographical, personal documents, such as letters, diaries, memoirs, etc. See: Anne van Mourik, ‘Between Lines and Lives: Using Ego-Documents to Study War and Violence’, NIOD Rewind Podcast on War & Violence (February 2024).

² Milan van Lange, Annelies van Nispen, and Carlijn Keijzer, ‘Handgeschreven “egodocumenten” automatisch transcriberen: Oorlog uit Eerste Hand: Oorlogsbrieven van het NIOD (1935-1950) digitaal’, *E-DATA & RESEARCH* 17, no. 1 (10 January 2022): 8; Tim de Haan, ‘Brieven- en dagboekencollectie van het NIOD Instituut voor Oorlogs-, Holocaust- en Genocidestudies’, Unesco, 1 November 2022, <https://www.unesco.nl/nl/nl-memory-world-register/brieven-en-dagboekencollectie-van-het-niod-instituut-voor-oorlogs>.

³ Terry Cook, ‘The Archive(s) Is a Foreign Country: Historians, Archivists, and the Changing Archival Landscape’, *The American Archivist* 74, no. 2 (2011): 609.

⁴ Joshua Sternfeld, ‘Archival Theory and Digital Historiography: Selection, Search, and Metadata as Archival Processes for Assessing Historical Contextualization’, *The American Archivist* 74, no. 2 (2011): 544–75.

⁵ Sue McKemmish, ‘Placing Records Continuum Theory and Practice’, *Archival Science* 1, no. 4 (1 December 2001): 333–59; Marieke Oprel and Marijke van Faassen, ‘Paper Trails to Private Lives: The Performative Power of Card Indexes through Time and Space’, in *Information and Power in History* (Routledge, 2020); Viviane Frings-Hessami, ‘The Societal Embeddedness of Records: Teaching the Meaning of the Fourth Dimension of the Records Continuum Model in Different Cultural Contexts’, *Archival Science* 21, no. 2 (1 June 2021): 139–54.

beyond their historical substance. The traces of how records are impacted by the so-called ‘curatorial voices’⁶ of various actors interacting with the records over the decades are identified to illuminate meaning-making interactions and how these precede, intersect, and interact with the practices historians use to find, analyze, and interpret historical records and write their academic articles or books.⁷

The case studies discussed in this contribution are part of ‘Collectie 247: Correspondentie’. These war letters are collected and curated by the NIOD Institute for War, Holocaust, and Genocide Studies since 1945. Most of the letters within the collection were written in the context of the German Occupation of the Netherlands during World War II and the War of Independence in Indonesia.

The collection consists predominantly of documents that were donated by individuals or families to the institute. The documents were acknowledged as ‘Memory of the World’ by UNESCO in 2022 and were digitised in the 2020-2023 project ‘First-Hand Accounts of War’.

The term ‘curatorial voices’ is here first and foremost used as a framework to identify the tactile traces that are left of the interventions of professional archivists and the different underlying choices and decisions they make in acquiring, categorizing, indexing, and describing collections of historical records in the archive. Investigating the ‘voices’ of these professionals has important epistemological benefits and methodological implications for historical scholarship, as the traces of these voices impact how scholars (can) interact with archival collections, and how they discover, select, concatenate, and interpret their sources.⁸

In the case of the NIOD’s war letters, these ‘voices’ are also the ones of many

different ‘amateur record-keepers’ – the people who received, kept, gathered, curated, and preserved – sometimes their own – letters in boxes, suitcases, and in the attics of their family homes. These record-keepers decided what was kept and what was thrown away. They sometimes added contextual information (metadata), or merged various kinds of records into a single collection, such as diaries, agendas, photographs, or other memorabilia. Sometimes they added their own perspectives and interpretations of the documents to the (sub)collection, e.g., in extensively annotated transcriptions or in elaborate donation letters (to the NIOD), while other custodians kept the original materials for decades by simply wrapping them in a rubber band.⁹ In particular the record-keeping habits of these private individuals, families, or small groups are often characterized by the absence of order or rigid systematics. This not only affirms the importance of careful and comprehensive archival curation, but also instigates a need for historians to unravel the traces of curatorial practices before historical egodocuments can be analyzed as source for historical insight, evidence, or argumentation.¹⁰

In the practice of using historical ‘egodocuments’ in historical scholarship and research, particularly when working with digital representations of such collections, gathering sufficient insight in record provenance and (past) curatorial actions can be quite complicated.¹¹ Therefore, this contribution aims to provide some guiding principles for studying the intricate web of considerations, decisions, and ‘curatorial voices’ related to the historical preservation, archiving, curation, digitisation, research, and (re-)use of egodocuments and the possible implications for historical scholarship. As such, this contribution aims to take the first steps in developing an expanded source-critical practice.

⁶ James Baker and Andrew Salway, ‘Curatorial Labour, Voice and Legacy: Mary Dorothy George and the Catalogue of Political and Personal Satires, 1930–54*’, *Historical Research* 93, no. 262 (1 November 2020): 769–85.; Andrew Salway and James Baker, ‘Investigating Curatorial Voice with Corpus Linguistic Techniques: The Case of Dorothy George and Applications in Museological Practice’, 6 July 2020.

⁷ Joy Parr, ‘Gender History and Historical Practice’, *The Canadian Historical Review* 76, no. 3 (September 1995): 371–72.

⁸ Katharina Hering, ‘Provenance Meets Source Criticism’, *Journal of Digital Humanities* 3, no. 2 (2014).

⁹ Ilari Taskinen, ‘Social Lives in Letters: Finnish Soldiers’ Epistolary Relationships, Intimate Practices, and Emotionality in World War II’ (PhD thesis, Tampere, Tampere University, 2021), 35–36.

¹⁰ Cook, ‘The Archive(s) Is a Foreign Country: Historians, Archivists, and the Changing Archival Landscape’, 626.

¹¹ Tim Hitchcock, ‘Confronting the Digital’, *Cultural and Social History* 10, no. 1 (1 March 2013): 14; Katharina Hering, ‘Provenance Meets Source Criticism’, *Journal of Digital Humanities* 3, no. 2 (2014).

Keywords

Source Criticism, Archival Transformations, Personal Correspondence, Digitisation, Records Continuum Model, Provenance, Curatorial Voice, World War II

Bio

Dr. Milan van Lange works as a digital history researcher at the NIOD. He defended his PhD-thesis ‘Emotional Imprints of War: A Computer-assisted Analysis of Emotions in Dutch Parliamentary Debates, 1945–1989’ at Utrecht University in 2021. He led the project ‘First-Hand Accounts of War’ from 2020 till 2023. Van Lange’s research interests are at the intersection of the social history of war and violence, digital history and methodology, source criticism, and studying the implications of (digital) transformations of the archive.

Bibliography

- Baker, James, and Andrew Salway. ‘Curatorial Labour, Voice and Legacy: Mary Dorothy George and the Catalogue of Political and Personal Satires, 1930–54*’. *Historical Research* 93, no. 262 (1 November 2020): 769–85. <https://doi.org/10.1093/hisres/htaa026>.
- Cook, Terry. ‘The Archive(s) Is a Foreign Country: Historians, Archivists, and the Changing Archival Landscape’. *The American Archivist* 74, no. 2 (2011): 600–632.
- Frings-Hessami, Viviane. ‘The Societal Embeddedness of Records: Teaching the Meaning of the Fourth Dimension of the Records Continuum Model in Different Cultural Contexts’. *Archival Science* 21, no. 2 (1 June 2021): 139–54. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10502-020-09349-6>.
- Haan, Tim de. ‘Brieven- en dagboekencollectie van het NIOD Instituut voor Oorlogs-, Holocaust- en Genocidestudies’. Unesco, 1 November 2022. <https://www.unesco.nl/nl/nl-memory-world-register/brieven-en-dagboekencollectie-van-het-niod-instituut-voor-oorlogs>.
- Hering, Katharina. ‘Provenance Meets Source Criticism’. *Journal of Digital Humanities* 3, no. 2 (2014). <https://journalofdigitalhumanities.org/3-2/provenance-meets-source-criticism/>.
- Hitchcock, Tim. ‘Confronting the Digital’. *Cultural and Social History* 10, no. 1 (1 March 2013): 9–23. <https://doi.org/10.2752/147800413X13515292098070>.
- Lange, Milan van, Annelies van Nispen, and Carlijn Keijzer. ‘Handgeschreven “egodocumenten” automatisch transcriberen: Oorlog uit Eerste Hand: Oorlogsbrieven van het NIOD (1935–1950) digitaal’. *E-DATA & RESEARCH* 17, no. 1 (10 January 2022): 8.
- McKemmish, Sue. ‘Placing Records Continuum Theory and Practice’. *Archival Science* 1, no. 4 (1 December 2001): 333–59. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02438901>.
- Mourik, Anne van. ‘Between Lines and Lives: Using Ego-Documents to Study War and Violence’. NIOD Rewind Podcast on War & Violence, n.d.
- Oprel, Marieke, and Marijke van Faassen. ‘Paper Trails to Private Lives: The Performative Power of Card Indexes through Time and Space’. In *Information and Power in History*. Routledge, 2020.
- Parr, Joy. ‘Gender History and Historical Practice’. *The Canadian Historical Review* 76, no. 3 (September 1995): 354–76.
- Salway, Andrew, and James Baker. ‘Investigating Curatorial Voice with Corpus Linguistic Techniques: The Case of Dorothy George and Applications in Museological Practice’, 6 July 2020. <https://doi.org/10.29311/mas.v18i2.3175>].
- Sternfeld, Joshua. ‘Archival Theory and Digital Historiography: Selection, Search, and Metadata as Archival Processes for Assessing Historical Contextualization’. *The American Archivist* 74, no. 2 (2011): 544–75.
- Taskinen, Ilari. ‘Social Lives in Letters: Finnish Soldiers’ Epistolary Relationships, Intimate Practices, and Emotionality in World War II’. PhD thesis, Tampere University, 2021.